

19. Uluslararası Dil, Edebiyat ve Kültür Araştırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

Proceedings Book of The 19th International Congress on Language, Literature and Culture Research

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ÖN SÖZ

19. Uluslararası Dil, Edebiyat ve Kültür Araştırmaları Kongresi, 04–08 Kasım 2025 tarihleri arasında Türkiye'nin Antalya kentinde gerçekleştirilmiş; dil, edebiyat ve kültür alanlarını disiplinlerarası bir bakış açısıyla ele alan önemli bir bilimsel buluşma platformu olmuştur. Kongre, Saybiller Topluluğu organizasyonunda; başta Mardin Artuklu Üniversitesi (Türkiye) ve Carthage University (Tunus) olmak üzere çeşitli yükseköğretim kurumlarının akademik desteğiyle düzenlenmiştir.

Kongre kapsamında, farklı akademik gelenekleri ve araştırma perspektiflerini temsil eden 6 farklı ülkeden davetli konuşmacı bilim insanlarıyla buluşturulmuştur. Ayrıca Türkçe, İngilizce ve Arapça dillerinde yapılan çağrılarla geniş bir uluslararası katılım sağlanmıştır. Bu çok dilli ve kapsayıcı çağrı süreci sonucunda gönderilen bildiriler, bilimsel etik ve kalite ilkeleri doğrultusunda hakem değerlendirme sürecinden geçirilmiştir. Yapılan değerlendirmeler neticesinde Türkiye'den 34, Türkiye dışından ise Birleşik Arap Emirlikleri, Cezayir, Endonezya, Fas, Filistin, Irak, İran, Katar, Kuveyt, Mısır, Suriye, Suudi Arabistan Krallığı ve Ürdün olmak üzere 13 farklı ülkeden 114 bildiri, kongre programında yer almış; böylece toplam 148 bildiri bilim dünyasıyla paylaşılmıştır.

Bu kongre kitabında yer alan çalışmalar; dil, edebiyat ve kültür araştırmalarında güncel kuramsal yaklaşımları, özgün analizleri ve farklı coğrafyalardan gelen akademik deneyimleri bir araya getirmektedir. Kongre süreci, özellikle uluslararası ve kültürlerarası iş birliğine dayalı araştırmaların bilimsel bilginin evrenselleşmesi ve akademik etkileşimin sürdürülebilirliği açısından taşıdığı önemi bir kez daha ortaya koymuştur.

Bu bağlamda araştırmacıların; disiplinlerarası çalışmalara daha fazla yönelmeleri, ortak projeler ve çok yazarlı uluslararası yayınlar aracılığıyla akademik etkileşimi güçlendirmeleri ve farklı dillerde bilimsel üretim yaparak çalışmalarının görünürlüğünü artırmaları önem arz etmektedir. Üniversitelerin, araştırma merkezlerinin ve diğer paydaşların ise genç araştırmacıları destekleyen, uluslararası akademik ağları teşvik eden ve nitelikli bilimsel üretimi sürdürülebilir kılan yapılar oluşturmaya devam etmeleri gerekmektedir.

Bu kongrenin ve elinizdeki kitabın; alan yazınına anlamlı katkılar sunmasını, yeni akademik iş birliklerine zemin hazırlamasını ve dil, edebiyat ile kültür araştırmalarında nitelikli bilimsel üretimi teşvik etmesini temenni eder; kongrenin gerçekleştirilmesinde emeği geçen tüm kurumlara, hakemlere, davetli konuşmacılara ve değerli araştırmacılara teşekkür ederiz.

Prof. Dr. Gehan M. Anwar Deeb - October 6 University

Düzenleme Kurulu Başkanı

PREFACE

The 19th International Congress on Language, Literature, and Culture Research, held in Antalya, Türkiye, between November 4–8, 2025, constituted a significant academic platform that brought together studies in language, literature, and culture within an interdisciplinary framework. The congress was organized by the Saybilder Community, with the academic support of several higher education institutions, most notably Mardin Artuklu University and Carthage University.

Within the scope of the congress, invited speakers from six different countries met with scholars representing diverse academic traditions and research perspectives. In addition, calls for papers were announced in Turkish, English, and Arabic, enabling broad international participation. Following these multilingual calls, the submitted papers underwent a peer-review process conducted in accordance with scientific and ethical standards. As a result of the evaluations, a total of 148 papers were included in the scientific program, comprising 34 papers from Türkiye and 114 papers from 13 different countries, namely the United Arab Emirates, Algeria, Indonesia, Morocco, Palestine, Iraq, Iran, Qatar, Kuwait, Egypt, Syria, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, and Jordan.

The studies presented in this proceedings book brought together contemporary theoretical approaches, original analyses, and diverse academic experiences from different geographical regions in the fields of language, literature, and culture. In particular, the congress clearly demonstrated the importance of international and intercultural collaborative research, emphasizing its crucial role in the universal dissemination of scientific knowledge and the establishment of sustainable interaction among different academic traditions.

In this context, researchers are encouraged to further engage in interdisciplinary studies, to strengthen academic interaction through joint projects and international co-authored publications, and to enhance the visibility of their research by producing scholarly work in multiple languages. Universities, research centers, and other stakeholders are likewise encouraged to continue supporting early-career researchers, fostering international academic networks, and developing sustainable structures for high-quality scientific production.

It is our sincere hope that this congress and the present proceedings book will contribute meaningfully to the existing literature, inspire new academic collaborations, and promote rigorous scientific research in the fields of language, literature, and cultural studies. We would like to express our gratitude to all institutions, reviewers, invited speakers, and distinguished researchers who contributed to the successful realization of this congress.

Prof. Dr. Gehan M. Anwar Deeb - October 6 University
Chair of the Organizing Committee

المقدمة

انعقد المؤتمر الدولي التاسع عشر للغة والأدب والدراسات الثقافية في مدينة أنطاليا - تركيا خلال الفترة من 4 إلى 8 نوفمبر 2025، وشكّل منصة علمية متميزة جمعت دراسات اللغة والأدب والثقافة في إطارٍ متعدد التخصصات. وقد نُظّم المؤتمر من قِبَل مجتمع سايبيلدر (Saybilder)، بدعمٍ علمي من عدد من مؤسسات التعليم العالي، وفي مقدمتها جامعة ماردين أرتقلو وجامعة قرطاج (Carthage University).

وشهد المؤتمر مشاركة متحدثين مدعويين من ست دول مختلفة، حيث التقى هؤلاء بنخبة من الباحثين الذين يمثلون مدارس أكاديمية ورؤى بحثية متنوعة. كما أُطلقت دعوات المشاركة باللغات التركية والإنجليزية والعربية، ما أسهم في تحقيق مشاركة دولية واسعة. وبعد ذلك، خضعت البحوث المقدّمة لعملية تحكيم علمي وفق المعايير الأكاديمية والأخلاقية المعتمدة. وأسفرت هذه العملية عن إدراج 148 بحثاً ضمن البرنامج العلمي، منها 34 بحثاً من تركيا و 114 بحثاً من 13 دولة هي: الإمارات العربية المتحدة، الجزائر، إندونيسيا، المغرب، فلسطين، العراق، إيران، قطر، الكويت، مصر، سوريا، المملكة العربية السعودية، والأردن.

وقد جمعت الدراسات الواردة في هذا الكتاب بين أحدث المقاربات النظرية، والتحليلات الأصيلة، والتجارب الأكاديمية المتنوعة من مختلف المناطق الجغرافية في مجالات اللغة والأدب والثقافة. كما أبرز المؤتمر بوضوح أهمية البحوث القائمة على التعاون الدولي والتفاعل الثقافي، لما لها من دور محوري في تعميم المعرفة العلمية وبناء تفاعل أكاديمي مستدام بين التقاليد العلمية المختلفة.

وانطلاقاً من نتائج هذا اللقاء العلمي، يُشجّع الباحثون على توسيع نطاق الدراسات البيئية، وتعزيز المشاريع المشتركة، والإسهام في النشر العلمي الدولي المشترك، إضافة إلى الإنتاج البحثي متعدد اللغات بما يزيد من انتشار الأبحاث وتأثيرها. كما تُدعى الجامعات ومراكز البحث وسائر الشركاء الأكاديميين إلى مواصلة دعم الباحثين الشباب، وتعزيز الشبكات العلمية الدولية، وبناء هياكل مستدامة تضمن جودة واستمرارية الإنتاج العلمي.

وإذ نأمل أن يكون هذا المؤتمر وهذا الكتاب قد أسهما في إثراء الأدبيات العلمية وفتح آفاق جديدة للتعاون الأكاديمي، فإننا نتقدم بخالص الشكر والتقدير إلى جميع المؤسسات المشاركة، والمحكمين، والمتحدثين المدعويين، والباحثين الكرام الذين أسهموا في إنجاح هذا الحدث العلمي.

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Evaluative Scaling in Disaster Reporting: A Graduation-Based Analysis of English and Turkish News Texts

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Abstract

News discourse is often perceived as objective and emotionally neutral, functioning as a factual record of events. However, linguistic evidence suggests that news reports strategically manipulate the intensity, precision, and evaluation to shape audience perception. Within the framework of Appraisal Theory (Martin & White, 2005), this study examines how Graduation is employed in English and Turkish media reports of the 2025 Kartalkaya hotel fire, one of Turkey's deadliest disasters. Graduation refers to the linguistic mechanisms through which speakers or writers scale meanings up or down, thereby modulating emotional tone, rhetorical emphasis, or ideological alignment.

A mixed-methods research design was adopted, drawing on two corpora comprising 30 news articles (15 in English and 15 in Turkish) published within the three-week period following the incident. Each text was analyzed to identify linguistic realizations of Graduation and determine their role in shaping stance and intensity in news narratives with particular attention to lexical and grammatical patterns used to intensify or soften evaluations, quantify harm, or highlight institutional blame and heroism.

Findings show that Graduation is a central resource in both corpora, with Force particularly Intensification serving as the dominant means of dramatizing danger, foregrounding emotional impact, and amplifying the perceived severity of the disaster. Quantification, especially numerical scaling of casualties, damage, and institutional response, is also widely used but appears more frequently in the Turkish corpus. Focus resources reveal notable cross-linguistic contrasts: English reports regularly employ categorical sharpening to assert evaluative certainty, while Turkish texts display a broader stylistic repertoire by combining sharpening with occasional softening. These patterns reflect distinct journalistic traditions: English outlets favor direct, assertive stance-taking, whereas Turkish outlets integrate emotional proximity, numerical precision, and varied degrees of epistemic commitment. Overall, the study demonstrates that evaluative scaling is integral to constructing urgency, moral accountability, and narrative framing in disaster reporting and underscores the value of Graduation analysis for cross-linguistic media research.

Keywords: Appraisal Theory, Graduation, media discourse, evaluative language, cross-cultural comparison

Introduction

News discourse is frequently presented as factual, neutral and objective; however, a substantial body of research has shown that news language is inherently evaluative and shaped by institutional norms, cultural expectations and ideological orientations (Bednarek, 2006, 2016; Cotter, 2010; Richardson, 2007). Journalists do not simply recount events: they frame them through lexical, syntactic and discursive choices that foreground certain aspects of reality while backgrounding others (Bell, 1991; van Dijk, 1988, 2013). This tendency becomes especially visible in the context of disaster reporting, where linguistic resources are strategically used to convey severity, human suffering, urgency and institutional responsibility (Pantti et al., 2012). Such reporting demonstrates the inherently evaluative nature of news language and creates a fertile ground for investigating how intensity and emphasis are scaled.

Within this broader research, Appraisal Theory (Martin & White, 2005) has developed into a prominent analytical framework for examining how writers and speakers encode attitudes, negotiate dialogic space and modulate the strength of evaluative meanings. Although much Appraisal-based research has focused on Attitude and Engagement (e.g., Çakır Sarı, 2025; Huang, 2020; Jin, 2019; Wu & Zhao, 2018), less systematic attention has been paid to Graduation, the subsystem concerned with “the semantics of scaling” (Martin & White, 2005, p. 135). White (2025) underscores the analytical value of Appraisal Theory for examining how journalists construct point of view and persuasive effect. His analysis shows that both straight news and opinion writing rely on attitudinal and gradational resources to guide readers’ interpretations, even when explicit evaluation is minimized. By juxtaposing a hard-news report with an editorial covering the same event, White demonstrates how Graduation scales the intensity and significance of key meanings, while Engagement manages dialogic positioning and alternative viewpoints. Viewed collectively, these mechanisms reveal journalism’s rhetorical force. Crucially, White argues that analyzing news and commentary within a unified evaluative framework moves beyond conventional assumptions of journalistic “objectivity” and “factuality,” bringing to light the systematic ways in which stance, alignment and ideological perspective are constructed through discourse.

Cross-linguistic studies have shown that media cultures differ in the strategies they use to scale evaluative meanings (Arunsirot, 2012; Klimaya, 2016; Liu & Stevenson, 2013). Although the evaluative dimension of news has been widely documented, the specific mechanisms by which journalists scale intensity, magnitude and categorical precision are much less understood. Prior Appraisal studies have largely centered on Attitude or Engagement, leaving Graduation, responsible for modulating evaluative force, relatively underexplored. A cross-linguistic investigation of Graduation is therefore timely and necessary, particularly in relation to disaster reporting. The 2025 Kartalkaya hotel fire, one of the most devastating disasters in recent Turkish history, provides an ideal empirical context for such an investigation. Examining the patterned use of Graduation in this context enables a deeper understanding of how media outlets construct severity, urgency and blame, and how these constructions vary across languages and national media systems. By analyzing Force and Focus resources in English and Turkish reporting, this study offers new insights into culturally embedded rhetorical practices and demonstrates the analytical value of Graduation in identifying subtle evaluative cues that shape public interpretation of disasters. In doing so, the study contributes to the expanding research on evaluative language in media discourse and advances cross-cultural understandings of journalistic storytelling.

Theoretical Framework: Appraisal Theory

This study is grounded in Martin and White’s (2005) Appraisal Theory, which builds on Halliday’s (1994) Systemic Functional Grammar (SFG) to model the interpersonal metafunction of language. SFG provides a multidimensional view of texts, accounting for semantic, pragmatic and syntactic features, and explicates how clauses function within broader discourse structures. Its account of how meaning is organized in

context has been instrumental in comparative linguistic studies, enabling researchers to trace cross-linguistic and intertextual similarities and differences (Teich, 2001).

As illustrated in Figure 1, Appraisal Theory comprises three subsystems, Engagement, Attitude and Graduation, each addressing a different dimension of interpersonal meaning (Martin & White, 2005). Engagement concerns the sourcing of voices and the negotiation of dialogic space. Attitude encompasses affect, judgment and appreciation, capturing how texts evaluate emotions, behaviors and phenomena. Graduation, the focus of this study, regulates the intensity and prototypicality of meanings. Graduation consists of two main domains: Force and Focus. Force scales meanings up or down and includes both *intensification* and *quantification*. Intensification modifies qualities, processes or modalities (e.g., *slightly misleading*, *utterly devastated*, *prices skyrocketed*). These resources may be realized through dedicated intensifiers, infused lexical choices (*terrified*, *ecstatic*), or repetition. Quantification applies to entities and circumstances, covering number, size, mass, distribution and proximity (e.g., *a huge crowd*, *heavy losses*, *widespread anger*). Martin and White (2005) also highlight the role of lexical metaphors such as *a flood of complaints* as powerful quantifying devices.

Figure 1. Primary sources in Appraisal Theory (Martin & White, 2005)

Focus adjusts categorical boundaries by sharpening or softening prototypicality. Expressions such as *a real disaster*, *a true friend* or *pure madness* sharpen category membership, presenting the referent as a central or defining instance. Softening expressions (e.g., *a kind of negligence*, *some sort of crisis*) push meanings toward the margins of a category, often used to hedge or mitigate claims. Focus resources frequently interact with Attitude, strengthening or moderating evaluative force depending on context.

Graduation thus plays an important role in how Attitude and Engagement are realized, determining not only what is evaluated but also the degree of evaluation and its interpersonal consequences. It enables analysts to trace how texts build evaluative prosodies, dramatize events and negotiate alignment with readers. In this respect, by examining Force and Focus in detail, this study contributes to identifying how evaluative meanings are scaled in Turkish and English disaster reporting.

Literature Review

Evaluation, Appraisal, and Graduation in Disaster News Discourse

Research on journalistic reporting increasingly shows that news language does far more than recount events: it evaluates, interprets and frames crises in culturally patterned ways. News texts systematically embed evaluation, even when overt stance markers are minimized (Badnarek, 2006, pp. 42–45). Work grounded in Appraisal Theory (Martin & White, 2005) has been especially influential in demonstrating how journalists draw on Attitude, Engagement and Graduation to shape interpretations of harm, responsibility and emotional impact.

A growing number of studies highlight cross-cultural variation in attitudinal meaning. Puspita and Pranoto's (2021) analysis of 100 Japanese disaster reports, for instance, found Judgment to be the dominant evaluative resource, followed by Appreciation and Affect. Their results suggest that Japanese newspapers place greater emphasis on assessing institutional performance and social behaviour than on depicting victims' emotions. Liu and Stevenson's (2013) comparison of Chinese and Australian earthquake reporting similarly revealed different evaluative preferences: Chinese outlets tended to foreground Judgment, while Australian media relied more on Appreciation to convey the significance of the disaster. Zhang (2015) shows that later China Daily reports employed more affective and dialogic resources, marking a move toward more human-centred coverage. Alongside these Appraisal studies, CDA research by Klimava (2016) demonstrates how ideological positioning shapes crisis narratives, in his case, international reporting on the Ukraine conflict, showing how identical events can be framed through competing rhetorical strategies depending on political interests.

Within this broader field, Graduation has emerged as a particularly useful lens for understanding how news discourse conveys scale, urgency and moral force. Because disasters require journalists to communicate magnitude and escalation, Graduation resources, especially intensification, quantification and sharpening, play a central role. Early work by Arunsirot (2012) shows how Thai political commentary uses infused lexis, repetition and quantification to amplify emotional and ideological meanings. Altındış (2025) identifies a similar pattern in historical rhetoric, demonstrating how intensification and quantification heighten moral impact, while selective softening exposes broader ideological tensions.

Empirical studies of news reporting further confirm the centrality of Graduation. Wan (2024) observes that online news and social-media discourse about Chinese cultural artefact repatriation relies heavily on quantification and completion to scale the cultural and moral significance of repatriation claims. Fan's (2020) analysis of China Daily shows that Force resources, particularly comparison, attitudinal lexis, repetition and numerical data, are routinely used to shape positivity, foreground national progress and naturalize official value positions. In her study, Focus sharpening and softening help shape typicality and signal alignment or critique.

Research from African media provides a different angle. Nalwoga (2025) finds that Ugandan hard-news reporters often rely on covert Graduation strategies, metaphor, euphemism, repetition and compounded action sequences, to criticize police misconduct while maintaining an appearance of neutrality in politically sensitive contexts. These strategies allow journalists to intensify judgment without explicit evaluative statements. Likewise, studies in political and crime reporting show similar tendencies. Xia (2021) demonstrates that political news favours Force (intensification and quantification) over Focus, signalling a preference for strong assertions, urgency and certainty. Darmawan et al. (2022) report that Indonesian crime news often uses sharpening epithets and quantification to dramatize events and intensify perceptions of culpability.

Taken together, this body of work highlights three consistent themes. First, evaluative choices in disaster news are strongly shaped by cultural and institutional norms. Second, Graduation plays a decisive role in constructing the emotional and moral weight of crises, often more subtly than overt attitudinal language. Third, journalists across diverse media systems use both explicit and concealed gradational strategies to manage emotional resonance, institutional critique and political risk. Within this broader context, examining how English and Turkish news outlets reported the 2025 Kartalkaya hotel fire provides an opportunity to investigate how two distinct media cultures scale intensity, quantify harm and articulate responsibility in a major national disaster.

Evaluation and Appraisal in Turkish Media Discourse

Research on Turkish media discourse has increasingly drawn on Appraisal Theory to understand how evaluative meanings are shaped by political identity, institutional affiliation and cultural norms. One recent contribution is Erkirtay's (2025) paratextual analysis of Turkish translations of disaster-related headlines, which shows that attitudinal meanings are systematically reconfigured during translation. Although the study is framed within the Attitude subsystem, it demonstrates that Turkish headlines frequently amplify affective load and rhetorical impact relative to their English counterparts. While Appreciation values may be tempered, Judgment resources, particularly those implicating governmental responsibility, tend to be strengthened, suggesting a pattern of up-scaled evaluation in politically sensitive contexts. Ersoyoğlu (2024) conducted an Appraisal-based analysis of 455 speeches delivered by key figures in the Russia-Ukraine war, including Putin, Zelenskyy, Lavrov and Kuleba, and found that Judgment was the most frequently employed Attitude resource, whereas Appreciation appeared least often. The study shows that Russian speakers predominantly foreground positive self-presentation, while Ukrainian speakers rely more heavily on negative other-presentation, revealing contrasting evaluative strategies shaped by the conflict's ideological dynamics.

Earlier work on opinion journalism similarly documents the dominance of Judgment in Turkish media. Ercan and Dizdarıcı (2016) show that negative Social Sanction is especially prominent in the evaluation of political actors and institutions, while Aydın and Ercan (2022) demonstrate how Engagement strategies structure ideological alignment through dialogic expansion and contraction. Studies of political and family-policy discourse (Uçar & Yalçın, 2014; Yalçın Çakmak, 2014) further reveal how government-affiliated narratives often strengthen Appreciation and institutional legitimacy by calibrating evaluative meanings through Graduation. Research on gender-based violence (Özmen, 2019) also underscores the central role of Judgment, particularly in assigning responsibility and moralizing social issues. While previous studies cover a wide range of evaluative practices, the Graduation subsystem remains comparatively underexplored in Turkish media studies.

Much of the existing cross-linguistic Appraisal research has concentrated on Attitude, especially Judgment, or on Engagement in political communication (Ercan & Dizdarıcı, 2016; Aydın & Ercan, 2022; Can & Ercan, 2020). Meanwhile, comparative research on disaster reporting such as Liu and Stevenson's (2013) English-Chinese study demonstrates the importance of scaling mechanisms for representing magnitude, accountability and emotional intensity. However, similar investigations involving Turkish media have not yet been developed. These gaps motivate the present study, which places the Graduation subsystem at the centre of analysis and offers a corpus-based comparison of Turkish and English reporting on the 2025 Kartalkaya hotel fire. Situating Graduation within broader patterns of evaluative practice allows for a richer understanding of how journalists construct severity, blame and emotional proximity through gradational choices. Aligned with this aim, the study addresses the following research questions:

- How do English and Turkish media reports differ in their use of graduation resources in covering the Kartalkaya fire?

- How do media-specific orientations (e.g., Anadolu Ajansı, Hürriyet, Cumhuriyet; BBC, Reuters, The New York Times) reflect distinct discursive choices in the evaluative scaling of the event?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a mixed-methods design that integrates qualitative and quantitative components. The primary analytic tool was content analysis. Although often associated with qualitative inquiry, content analysis is widely recognized as a hybrid method because it can incorporate quantitative indicators alongside interpretive examination. Robert and Bouillaguet (1997) describe content analysis as a methodological framework with both qualitative and quantitative dimensions, designed to identify, classify, and interpret salient elements within texts or discourses. Simon and Burstein (1985) likewise emphasize that the method involves assigning written or spoken expressions to analytically defined categories and then systematically evaluating the frequency of their occurrence.

The qualitative component relies on Appraisal Theory (Martin & White, 2005), with particular attention to the Graduation subsystem, to conduct detailed textual analysis of how evaluative meanings are scaled in disaster reporting. This involves examining the linguistic realization of Force and Focus and identifying how journalists intensify, soften or otherwise calibrate evaluation in their coverage of the Kartalkaya Hotel fire. The qualitative analysis is complemented by quantitative frequency counts and proportional comparisons of Graduation resources across the English and Turkish subcorpora.

Sample

The sample consists of 30 news reports published in January 2025 in response to the Kartalkaya Hotel fire. The corpus includes 15 Turkish texts drawn from Anadolu Ajansı, Hürriyet, Cumhuriyet, Yeni Akit and Sözcü, and 15 English texts published by Associated Press, Reuters, BBC, The Guardian and The New York Times. All articles were retrieved from official news websites or publicly accessible digital archives shortly after the incident.

To ensure consistency in genre and register, the corpus includes only straight news reports. Opinion columns, editorials and in-depth analyses were excluded. Syndicated wire-service duplicates were also removed to ensure that each text represented an independent journalistic product. This comparative sample provides a suitable basis for examining how two linguistically and culturally distinct media systems scale evaluative meaning in disaster reporting.

Data Collection Tools and Process

Data collection proceeded through a structured search of the selected news organizations' official websites and publicly accessible archives. Only articles directly reporting on the Kartalkaya fire were eligible. A careful screening process ensured topic uniformity and eliminated duplicate wire-service content across outlets.

All eligible texts were downloaded in a uniform format and saved as plain-text files. The articles were then organized into two subcorpora, Turkish and English, to support systematic comparison. This cross-linguistic organization enables a focused examination of how evaluative intensity, institutional accountability and emotional framing differ across media environments with distinct cultural and journalistic norms.

Data Analysis

The analysis was conducted within the Appraisal framework formulated by Martin and White (2005), with particular emphasis on the subsystem of Graduation, which encompasses the resources through which speakers and writers scale intensity, quantity, and prototypicality. In line with this framework, all relevant linguistic items were identified and coded according to the established categories of Force and Focus.

To ensure consistency and analytic reliability, a Graduation Coding Manual was prepared specifically for this study. The manual sets out operational definitions, decision rules, boundary criteria, and corpus-specific examples for each subcategory. Its development followed a multi-step process: (1) extraction of preliminary examples from the pilot corpus; (2) refinement of coding distinctions through comparison with the original descriptions in Martin and White (2005); and (3) finalization of category descriptors and annotation procedures. This manual served as the reference point throughout the coding process and guided all subsequent qualitative and quantitative decisions. Graduation resources were coded using the established taxonomy:

Force

- Intensification (quality, process)
- Quantification (number, size/mass, distribution, proximity)

Focus

- Sharpening
- Softening

Each text was read multiple times to identify lexical, grammatical and metaphorical forms that scaled intensity, quantified damage, heightened urgency or adjusted categorical boundaries. Expressions modifying evaluative strength or precision constituted the unit of analysis. Force was coded for intensification and quantification in terms of number, size or mass, spatial or temporal distribution and proximity. Focus captured shifts in prototypicality through sharpening or softening. This coding scheme is consistent with previous Appraisal-based analyses of discourse (Hood & Martin, 2005). Coding was conducted manually by the researcher. To ensure analytical consistency, an intra-rater reliability procedure was employed: the entire dataset was coded twice, with a one-month interval between coding rounds. The interval reduced memory effects and helped verify the stability of coding decisions. Any discrepancies identified across the two rounds were resolved through close re-examination of contextual features and refinement of category boundaries when necessary. This process enhances the internal reliability of the analysis, particularly important in studies conducted by a single coder.

Following annotation, frequency counts were generated to determine the distribution of Graduation resources in each language. Quantitative patterns were interpreted alongside qualitative observations to examine how scaling contributed to rhetorical functions such as dramatization, emotional proximity, quantification of harm and attribution of institutional responsibility. Comparative analysis involved assessing proportional differences between the English and Turkish subcorpora and examining how Graduation resources shaped distinct narrative constructions of the same disaster.

Ethical Considerations

All data were derived from publicly accessible news articles, and no personal, proprietary or sensitive information was collected. The study did not involve human participants or direct interaction with individuals; therefore, formal ethical approval was not required.

Limitations

Several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the corpus is relatively small and focuses on a single disaster event, which restricts the broader generalizability of the findings. Second, the study examines only textual data and does not incorporate multimodal elements such as headlines, photographs, videos or comment sections, all of which play important roles in framing disaster news. These limitations indicate that while the study offers valuable insights into linguistic scaling practices, the results should be interpreted within the contextual and methodological boundaries of the present dataset.

Results and Discussion

Qualitative Analysis of Graduation Resources

The analysis of English and Turkish reporting on the 2025 Kartalkaya hotel fire shows that Graduation is central to how journalists construct the scale, urgency and moral stakes of the disaster. The qualitative analysis demonstrates that both English and Turkish news reports strategically modulate intensity, quantity, and categorical precision to shape emotional, moral, and informational interpretations of the Kartalkaya fire. Table 1 outlines the full range of Graduation resources identified in the corpus, demonstrating how both Force and Focus contribute to the evaluative shaping of disaster news narratives.

Table 1. Graduation Resources (Force and Focus) in the Kartalkaya Fire News Corpus

Graduation Type	Subtype	Discoursal Function in Disaster News	Examples from English Corpus (ENG01–ENG15)	Examples from Turkish Corpus (TR01–TR15)
FORCE	Intensification – Quality	Amplifies emotional, moral or physical impact; dramatizes severity	so terrifying, utterly chaotic, deeply distressing images, a horrifying scene	dehşet verici (<i>terrifying</i>) yürekleri dağlayan (<i>heartbreaking</i>) şoke edici manzaralar (<i>shocking scenes</i>), korkunç bir tablo (<i>a horrific picture</i>)
	Intensification – Process	Shows escalation and urgency of actions and events	flames tore through the hotel, smoke filled rooms, completely engulfed in smoke	alevler hızla yayıldı (<i>the flames spread rapidly</i>) duman koridorları kapladı (<i>smoke filled the corridors</i>) çalışmalar titizlikle yürütüldü (<i>the operations were carried out meticulously</i>) tamamen yanmış (<i>completely burned; entirely burned</i>)
	Quantification – Number	Scales magnitude of casualties, responders, and affected people	79 dead, 51 injured, 238 registered guests, six prosecutors	79 kişi hayatını kaybetti (<i>79 people lost their lives</i>) 52 naaş tespit edildi (<i>52 bodies were identified</i>) 171 araç (<i>171 vehicles</i>) 11 kişi gözaltında (<i>11 people in custody</i>)

	Quantification – Size/Mass	Highlights physical scale of damage or structural magnitude	12-story hotel, massive wooden façade, large smoke-filled lobby	12 katlı otel (12-story hotel) büyük hasar (<i>major/extensive damage</i>) otelin büyük bölümü ahşap (<i>a large portion of the hotel was wooden</i>)
	Quantification – Extent (Distribution: Time/Space)	Represents spread or duration across time or spatial scope	spread quickly through upper floors, raged throughout the building, smoke throughout the hotel”	10 saat süren müdahale (<i>a 10-hour intervention</i>) duman tüm koridorlara yayıldı (<i>smoke spread to all corridors</i>) binanın tamamına yayıldı (<i>spread throughout the entire building</i>)
	Quantification – Extent (Proximity: Time/Space)	Highlights temporal or spatial proximity of hazards or responses	near the start of a two-week break, nearby rooms engulfed	yangının çıktığı otelin yakınındaki başka otel (<i>another hotel near the one where the fire broke out</i>) bölgeye ulaşıldığında (<i>upon reaching the area</i>)
FOCUS	Sharpening	Intensifies categorical boundaries; signals precision or absoluteness	a real tragedy, clear failure of safety, the exact cause	tam bir facia (<i>a complete tragedy; an absolute disaster</i>) açık bir ihmal (<i>a clear case of negligence</i>) net bir hata (<i>a clear/definite mistake</i>)
	Softening	Mitigates certainty; hedges evaluations; introduces ambiguity	somewhat unclear, kind of chaotic	bir tür ihmal (<i>a kind of negligence</i>) kısmen net değil (<i>partially unclear; not entirely clear</i>) tam olarak belirlenemedi (<i>could not be fully determined</i>)

*Force: Intensification**Intensification–Quality*

Expressions that amplify emotional, physical, or moral impact are frequent in both corpora. English reports describe the event as “so terrifying” or “utterly chaotic,” invoking infused intensification where the lexeme itself carries an escalated emotional load. Turkish reporting employs similar constructions (e.g., “*yürekleri dağlayan görüntüler*” -heart-wrenching scenes) where affective lexis functions as an intensifying resource by strengthening the experiential impact.

- (1) Families described the scene as **so terrifying** that they could barely understand what was happening.
- (2) Survivors recounted **utterly chaotic** moments as they ran through smoke-filled corridors.
- (3) Witnesses called the fire **deeply shocking**, noting the rapid transformation of a holiday resort into a disaster zone.
- (4) Görgü tanıkları, yaşananları **yürekleri dağlayan görüntüler** olarak aktardı.
(*Witnesses described the scene as heart-wrenching images.*)

(5) Otelin içindeki koşullar **tam anlamıyla dehşet vericiydi**.
(Conditions inside the hotel were **truly terrifying**.)

(6) Yetkililer, gecenin **büyük bir panik** içinde geçtiğini belirtti.
(Officials stated that the night unfolded in **great panic**.)

The expressions in the examples (1-6) above align with Martin & White's classification of infused intensification, where amplification occurs through ideology-laden or emotion-laden vocabulary rather than through an explicit isolated intensifier (2005, p. 139). Intensification of qualities, "so terrifying," "utterly chaotic," amplifies emotional and moral impact, creating a strong affective frame around the event.

Intensification–Process

Many examples depict escalation, rapidity or urgency via dynamic verbal processes. English clauses such as "flames tore through the hotel," "smoke filled the corridors," or "rescuers worked frantically" construe unfolding danger as forceful and escalating. Turkish reports similarly note that "alevler hızla yayıldı" ("the flames spread rapidly") constructing urgency and danger through process escalation.

(7) Flames **tore through** the hotel within minutes of the first emergency calls.

(8) Thick smoke **rapidly filled** the upper floors, cutting off escape routes.

(9) Fire crews **worked frantically** as they attempted to reach those trapped inside.

(10) Alevler kısa sürede koridorları **hızla sardı**.
(The flames **quickly engulfed** the corridors.)

(11) Duman, binanın üst katlarını **birkaç dakika içinde kapladı**.
(Smoke **covered** the upper floors **within minutes**.)

(12) Ekipler, mahsur kalanlara ulaşmak için **aralıksız mücadele etti**.
(Teams **fought relentlessly** to reach those trapped.)

Intensification–Process examples such as "flames tore through the hotel," "smoke filled the corridors," illustrate process intensification in Martin and White's (2005) terms, in which the degree of activity or danger is escalated through verb choice and adverbial modification.

Force: Quantification

Number

Both corpora rely heavily on exact figures to scale the scope of casualties, rescue operations, and institutional responses. As illustrated in the sentences below quantification-number examples include "79 dead," "51 injured," "six prosecutors,"

(13) A total of **238 guests** were registered at the hotel on the night of the fire.

(14) Authorities confirmed **79 dead** and **51 injured** following hours of rescue efforts.

(15) The investigation now involves **six prosecutors** appointed by the regional judicial office.

- (16) Ekipler, enkazda **52 naaş** tespit edildiğini açıkladı.
(*Teams reported locating **52 bodies** in the debris.*)
- (17) Olay yerine **171 araç** ve yüzlerce personel sevk edildi.
(*A total of **171 vehicles** and hundreds of personnel were deployed.*)
- (18) Savcılık, soruşturma için **11 kişiyi** gözaltına aldı.
(*The prosecutor's office detained **11 individuals** for investigation.*)

Numerical scaling introduces factual precision while simultaneously amplifying the magnitude of loss and institutional involvement.

Size/Mass

English references such as “12-story hotel,” “large smoke-filled lobby,” or “massive wooden façade” foreground physical enormity. Turkish equivalents include “12 katlı otel” (12-story hotel) or “otelin büyük bölümü ahşap” (a large part of the hotel was wooden). These items function as mass/size quantifiers, intensifying the spatial scale of the disaster environment.

- (19) Firefighters struggled to contain flames in the hotel's **12-story structure**.
- (20) The lobby had become a **large smoke-filled** chamber by the time rescuers entered.
- (21) Witnesses described the **massive wooden façade** catching fire almost instantly.
- (22) Yangın, **12 katlı otelin** neredeyse tamamını etkiledi.
(*The fire affected nearly the entire **12-story hotel**.*)
- (23) Otelin **büyük bölümü ahşap** olduğu için alevler hızla yayıldı.
(*Since **a large part of the hotel was wooden**, the flames spread quickly.*)
- (24) Giriş katında **geniş bir duman hacmi** oluştu.
(*A **large volume of smoke** formed on the ground floor.*)

Extent: Distribution (Time/Space)

Temporal and spatial distribution express how far the fire or smoke spread, or how long rescue efforts persisted. English expressions like “*raged throughout the building*” or “*smoke throughout the hotel*” encode scope expansion, a key element of quantification.

- (25) The fire **spread throughout** the upper floors within minutes.
- (26) Smoke drifted **across the entire hotel**, making navigation nearly impossible.
- (27) Rescue operations continued for **more than ten hours** before the fire was contained.
- (28) Müdahale **10 saat boyunca** aralıksız sürdü.
(*The intervention continued for **10 hours straight**.*)
- (29) Duman **binanın tamamına yayıldı**.
(*Smoke **spread across the entire building**.*)
- (30) Alevler kısa sürede **tüm katlara** ulaştı.
(*The flames reached **all floors** in a short time.*)

Extent: Proximity (Time/Space)

Journalists scale meaning by highlighting closeness or immediacy. English reports note that the fire broke out “*near the start of a two-week break*,” while Turkish reports describe events occurring “*yakındaki başka bir otelde*” (*another hotel nearby*). Such proximal references mark relevance and intensify urgency.

- (31) The fire began **near the start** of a two-week holiday break.
- (32) Rooms **close to the ignition point** were engulfed within seconds.
- (33) A nearby resort evacuated guests as smoke drifted **toward adjacent buildings**.
- (34) Yangın, sömestr tatilinin **başlangıcına yakın** bir zamanda çıktı.
(*The fire broke out **near the beginning** of the school break.*)
- (35) Alevler, **yangının çıktığı odanın yakınındaki** bölümlere hızla yayıldı.
(*The flames spread quickly to areas **near the ignition room**.*)
- (36) **Yakındaki başka bir otelde** de tedbir amaçlı tahliye yapıldı.
(*A precautionary evacuation was carried out in **another hotel nearby**.*)

Framed by these observations, journalists rely extensively on Force, particularly Intensification, to heighten the perceived severity of the disaster, while Quantification is used to scale the magnitude of casualties, damage, and institutional action.

Focus: Sharpening and Softening

Sharpening

Sharpening constructs category membership as definitive or prototypical. English expressions such as “*a real tragedy*,” “*a clear failure of safety*,” or “*the exact cause*” establish moral clarity and categorical

precision. Turkish equivalents, “*tam bir facia*,” “*açık bir ihmal*,” “*net bir hata*”, serve similar functions, heightening evaluative certainty and responsibility attribution.

(37) Officials called the incident a **real tragedy**, demanding accountability.

(38) Experts described the failure as a **clear breach** of fire safety standards.

(39) Investigators are searching for **the exact cause** of the blaze.”

(40) Yetkililer olayı **tam bir facia** olarak nitelendirdi.

(*Authorities described the incident as a **complete disaster**.*)

(41) Uzmanlar, yaşananların **açık bir ihmal** olduğunu belirtti.

(*Experts stated that the incident was a **clear case of negligence**.*)

(42) Rapor, tesis yönetiminde **net bir hata** yapıldığını ortaya koydu.

(*The report revealed a **clear mistake** in facility management.*)

Softening

Softening resources mitigate certainty or construe weaker categorical membership. English examples include “*somewhat unclear*” or “*kind of chaotic*.” Turkish texts show limited use, with examples such as “*bir tür ihmal*,” “*kısmen net değil*,” or “*tam olarak belirlenemedi*.”

(43) The timeline remains **somewhat unclear**, according to investigators.

(44) Officials described the situation as a **kind of chaos**, though details are still emerging.

(45) The cause is **not entirely confirmed**, pending further analysis.

(46) Yetkililer bunun **bir tür ihmal** olabileceğini söyledi.

(*Officials said this may have been a **kind of negligence**.*)

(47) Olayın nedeninin **tam olarak belirlenemediği** ifade edildi.

(*It was stated that the cause of the incident **could not be fully determined**.*)

(48) Bazı kritik noktalar **kısmen net değil**.

(*Some critical details remain **partially unclear**.*)

These hedges introduce interpretive space, reduce commitment and temper strong claims, functions consistent with Martin & White’s discussion of softened prototypicality (2005, p. 139). Within this broader context, Focus resources contribute by sharpening categorical boundaries or, less frequently, softening evaluative commitment.

Together, these patterns suggest that the Kartalkaya findings closely mirror the evaluative dynamics outlined by Pantti et al. 2012. Both the Turkish and English corpora draw heavily on intensification, quantification, and sharpening. Pantti et al. 2012 describe how disaster coverage is shaped by classic news values such as magnitude, drama and elite relevance. These values frequently manifest linguistically through quantification, intensifiers and vivid process verbs, echoing the findings. English texts often rely on high-energy verbs and descriptive precision, (“flames tore through the hotel,” “smoke filled the corridors”), to dramatize the unfolding event, while Turkish coverage draws extensively on evaluative lexis, spatial scaling and temporal distribution (“10 saat süren müdahale” “a 10-hour intervention”) to foreground the severity of the crisis. Such patterns are consistent with Pantti et al.’s observation that

magnitude and drama are central to the narrative logic of disaster news. The authors' use of banal nationalism offers a productive lens for interpreting the corpus. The authors note that even routine news reporting subtly invokes the nation through habitual lexical choices, thereby reinforcing moral boundaries and collective identities. This perspective aligns closely with the marked prevalence of Focus: Sharpening in both English and Turkish reports, where categorical labels, such as “clear failure of safety” or “tam bir facia” (“a complete disaster”), construct moral clarity and assertively position institutional actors within a national narrative of responsibility and expectation.

3.2 Overall Distribution of Graduation Resources

The distribution of Graduation resources across the English and Turkish corpora is given in Table 2. A total of 324 instances were identified in the English subcorpus, compared with 356 in the Turkish subcorpus, indicating that both media systems rely heavily on evaluative scaling to report the Kartalkaya fire.

Table 2. Graduation Resources in English and Turkish Reports

Corpus	Force: Intensification (f / %)	Force: Quantification (f / %)	Focus: Sharpening (f / %)	Focus: Softening (f / %)	Total
English News (ENG01–ENG15)	178 / 54.9	78 / 24.1	68 / 21.0	0 / 0.0	324
Turkish News (TR01–TR15)	189 / 53.1	106 / 29.8	53 / 14.9	8 / 2.2	356

In both corpora, Force–Intensification is the most frequent category (54.9% in English; 53.1% in Turkish). This confirms previous research showing that journalists heighten emotional significance and situational urgency through intensified lexis in disaster coverage (Bednarek, 2006; Pantti et al., 2012). Arunsirot (2012) shows that Thai political commentaries regularly use infused lexis, repetition and metaphor to up-scale emotional and ideological meanings, with Graduation overwhelmingly functioning as an intensifying resource. A similar tendency is observed by Xia (2021) in political news and by Darmawan et al. (2022) in crime reporting in *The Jakarta Post*, where intensification and quantification dominate and sharpened epithets dramatize events and accentuate culpability. The Kartalkaya corpus fits this broader picture: when journalists cover high-stakes events, intensification becomes the default register for constructing seriousness, escalation and urgency. Thus, Intensification reinforces the severity of the event, legitimizes emergency response efforts and escalates public perception of crisis.

While both English and Turkish texts use quantification extensively, Turkish reports exhibit a notably higher rate of Quantification (29.8% vs. 24.1%). Turkish coverage frequently foregrounds casualty numbers, duration of intervention and scope of structural damage. Here, the Kartalkaya findings echo Wan's (2024) analysis of news and social media discourse on the repatriation of Chinese cultural artefacts. Wan demonstrates that quantification is used to scale the cultural and moral weight of repatriation claims and to intensify ideological positioning. Fan's (2020) work on *China Daily* similarly shows that numerical data and comparative forms are used to enhance positivity and foreground national progress, even within ostensibly objective hard news. In the Kartalkaya corpus, quantification does not primarily work to

celebrate national achievement, as in Fan's (2020) case, but it serves a comparable ideological function: it stabilizes the narrative, anchors it in apparently incontestable facts, and foregrounds institutional presence. Numbers make the fire legible as a crisis of a particular magnitude and, in doing so, shape how institutional performance is evaluated. Thus, Turkish Kartalkaya reports often deploy numerical scaling to assert factual gravity and underline institutional action.

The distribution of Focus resources shows a marked cross-linguistic contrast. Focus–Sharpening appears moderately in both corpora (21% in English; 14.9% in Turkish). However, Focus–Softening occurs only in Turkish reporting (2.5%), suggesting that Turkish outlets occasionally reduce categorical force or introduce epistemic caution, whereas English outlets maintain a consistently up-scaled and assertive evaluative stance. This aligns with descriptions of Anglo-American news discourse as favouring direct stance-taking and epistemic certainty, especially in crisis contexts where responsibility and failure are central (Cotter, 2010; Wahl-Jorgensen, 2020).

The findings indicate that both languages rely heavily on intensification to dramatize the disaster and construct emotional proximity. Turkish reporting, however, employs numerical scaling more frequently and exhibits a wider stylistic repertoire by occasionally mitigating claims. English reporting, by contrast, presents an evaluative profile characterized by strong intensification and categorical sharpening without hedging. These cross-linguistic patterns reflect broader journalistic tendencies: while English outlets emphasize dramatization and strong categorical assertion, Turkish outlets combine similar intensifying strategies with more frequent numerical precision and occasional epistemic caution. Taken together, these qualitative and quantitative findings show that Graduation resources function as a central mechanism through which both media systems construct urgency, assign blame, evaluate institutional action and generate emotional resonance in reporting on the Kartalkaya fire.

Distribution of Graduation Across English News Outlets

Table 3 presents the distribution of Graduation resources across the five English-language outlets. Across all sources, Force–Intensification is the dominant category, confirming the qualitative finding that English news coverage of the Kartalkaya fire is strongly oriented toward dramatization, urgency and emotional force. BBC and Reuters show the highest intensification counts (39 instances each, representing 57.4% and 53.4% of each outlet's Graduation use), frequently drawing on high-energy verbs and intensified descriptors to convey the rapid escalation and severity of the event. These patterns mirror earlier observations that English disaster reporting often heightens immediacy and emotional resonance through intensifying lexis (Bednarek, 2006; Pantti et al., 2012). The strong presence of intensification across both corpora is consistent with Bednarek's (2006) discussion of crisis reporting, where heightened lexis and high-energy verbal processes are routinely used to dramatize unfolding events and signal urgency (pp. 45–47).

Table 3. Graduation Categories in English Outlets

News Source	Force: Intensification (f / %)	Force: Quantification (f / %)	Focus: Sharpening (f / %)	Focus: Softening (f / %)	Total (f / %)
Associated Press (ENG01–ENG03)	35 / 68.6%	11 / 21.6%	5 / 9.8%	0 / 0.0%	51 / 100%
BBC (ENG04–ENG06)	39 / 55.7%	17 / 24.3%	14 / 20.0%	0 / 0.0%	70 / 100%
Reuters (ENG07–ENG09)	39 / 53.4%	17 / 23.3%	17 / 23.3%	0 / 0.0%	73 / 100%
The Guardian (ENG10–ENG12)	33 / 47.8%	19 / 27.5%	17 / 24.6%	0 / 0.0%	69 / 100%
New York Times (ENG13–ENG15)	32 / 52.5%	14 / 23.0%	15 / 24.6%	0 / 0.0%	61 / 100%

Force: Quantification constitutes the second most frequent category in all five outlets. It is particularly prominent in The Guardian (19 instances; 27.5%) and the BBC (17 instances; 24.3%), where numerical scaling, such as precise casualty figures, spatial descriptions, and institutional responses, contributes to the factual density of the coverage. This pattern reflects earlier observations that Anglo-American journalism frequently relies on quantification to support evidential authority and assertiveness in crisis reporting (Bednarek & Caple, 2012; Cotter, 2010). The frequent use of numerical detail mirrors Bednarek's (2006) finding that quantification serves not only to convey factual information but also to enhance evaluative force and construct newsworthiness (pp. 48–49).

Focus: Sharpening appears consistently across outlets, though less frequently than Force resources. The highest proportions occur in Reuters (17 instances; 23.3%), The Guardian (17 instances; 24.6%), and The New York Times (15 instances; 24.6%). Sharpening expressions in these texts include categorical assessments such as *"a real tragedy," "the exact cause,"* or explicit evaluations of safety failures. The marked reliance on categorical sharpening in the English reports aligns with Bednarek's (2006) observation that news writers often employ precise evaluative nouns and epithets to frame moral judgment and delineate responsibility (pp. 46–48).

A striking finding is the complete absence of Focus: Softening across all 15 English-language texts. This pattern resonates with established descriptions of Anglo-American news style, which is characterized by direct stance-taking, unequivocal attribution of responsibility, and clear delineation of factual claims (Wahl-Jorgensen, 2020). Softening expressions such as *"somewhat unclear"* or *"a kind of failure,"* though common in other linguistic traditions, were entirely absent in this corpus, indicating a cultural preference for epistemic certainty and reluctance to hedge evaluations in moments of crisis.

Taken together, the English-language results show a consistent orientation toward intensified, categorical, and numerically precise reporting. The findings confirm that Graduation resources, particularly intensification and sharpening, play a key role in shaping the affective and moral contours of English disaster narratives. The patterns observed in this study support Bednarek's (2006) claim that news

discourse is inherently evaluative, drawing on subtle linguistic cues to shape stance even when journalists avoid overt expressions of opinion (pp. 42–45).

Distribution of Graduation Across Turkish News Outlets

The stylistic tendencies within Turkish journalism are given in Table 4 and it demonstrates the distribution of Graduation categories across the five Turkish outlets in the corpus. Across all outlets, Force–Intensification emerges as the dominant resource, supporting the broader pattern observed in the overall Turkish corpus. This category is used extensively to heighten emotional impact, dramatize the unfolding crisis and foreground the severity of the event.

Hürriyet employs the highest proportion of intensification (41 instances; 66.1%), followed by Cumhuriyet (35 instances; 52.2%) and Sözcü (34 instances; 58.6%). These results indicate that mainstream Turkish outlets consistently favour intensified adjectives, adverbs and high-vigour process verbs to convey a vivid sense of escalation and emotional urgency. This aligns with previous research noting that Turkish crisis reporting typically foregrounds affective salience and collective emotional response.

Table 4. Attitude Categories in Turkish Outlets

News Source	Force: Intensification (f / %)	Force: Quantification (f / %)	Focus: Sharpening (f / %)	Focus: Softening (f / %)	Total (f / %)
Anadolu Ajansı (TR01–TR03)	52 / 49%	32 / 30.2%	22 / 20.8%	0 / 0.0%	106 / 100%
Cumhuriyet (TR04–TR06)	36 / 53.7%	15 / 22.4%	16 / 23.9%	0 / 0.0%	67 / 100%
Hürriyet (TR07–TR09)	41 / 66.1%	14 / 22.6%	7 / 11.3%	0 / 0.0%	62 / 100%
Sözcü (TR10–TR12)	34 / 58.6%	20 / 34.5%	4 / 6.9%	0 / 0.0%	58 / 100%
Yeni Akit (TR13–TR15)	26 / 41.3%	25 / 39.7%	4 / 6.3%	8 / 12.7%	63 / 100%

As in the English corpus, Force–Quantification is the second most frequent category; however, its distribution is more uneven across outlets. Anadolu Ajansı (32 instances; 30.2%) and Yeni Akit (25 instances; 39.7%) rely on quantification to a greater extent than other sources. The prominence of numerical scaling in Anadolu Ajansı, given its institutional role as a state news agency, is consistent with a reporting style that foregrounds official statements, operational updates and factual enumeration. Yeni Akit's heavy use of quantification similarly reflects a tendency to emphasise scope, numbers and procedural detail. In Sözcü and Cumhuriyet, quantification remains present but less dominant, contributing to the factual and numerical anchoring of the narrative while leaving intensification as the primary evaluative strategy.

Focus–Sharpening appears across all outlets but varies substantially in frequency. Anadolu Ajansı (22 instances; 20.8%) and Cumhuriyet (16 instances; 23.9%) show the highest use of sharpening expressions, which frequently signal categorical certainty or assign institutional responsibility. These markers reinforce moral clarity and evaluative precision, contributing to the construction of explicit narrative stances. These sharpened categories amplify moral judgment and make institutional evaluations more explicit, a pattern consistent with prior Appraisal-based research showing the dominance of Judgement in Turkish opinion and news discourse (Ercan & Dizdarci, 2016; Özmen, 2019). Hürriyet, Sözcü and Yeni Akit employ sharpening less frequently, though still in ways that underline key evaluative points in the narrative.

A notable divergence from the general pattern of strong up-scaling emerges in the case of Yeni Akit, the only outlet in the corpus that employs Focus–Softening (8 instances; 12.7%). Unlike the other four newspapers, which rely exclusively on sharpening and intensification, Yeni Akit introduces hedging expressions such as *bir tür ihmâl* (“a kind of negligence”) or *kısmen net değil* (“partially unclear”). This selective use of softening must be interpreted within the outlet’s broader political orientation: as a pro-government newspaper, Yeni Akit typically aligns its reporting with official narratives and avoids direct or categorical attribution of institutional fault. The presence of hedging thus appears to function as a discursive buffer that mitigates the force of evaluative judgments in contexts where explicit blame could politically implicate state authorities.

This pattern closely echoes the type of risk-managed evaluation described by Nalwoga (2025) in Ugandan hard-news reporting, where metaphor, euphemism and moderated critique enable journalists to signal negative judgments while maintaining the appearance of neutrality in politically constrained environments. Although the socio-political circumstances differ, Yeni Akit’s rhetorical balancing act suggests a comparable strategy: while its reporting employs the same up-scaling characteristic of Turkish disaster news—through extensive intensification and quantification—it strategically introduces softening at moments where direct institutional criticism would be politically delicate. This combination of heightened emotional force and targeted mitigation underscores how ideological alignment shapes the distribution of Graduation resources and demonstrates that evaluative stance in disaster reporting is not merely linguistic but also deeply embedded in the outlet’s political positioning.

Overall, these findings reveal several important interpretive patterns. First, intensification is the most pervasive Graduation strategy across all Turkish outlets, reflecting a reporting style that foregrounds emotional weight, dramatic escalation and the catastrophic nature of the fire. Second, quantification is used more prominently in Turkish reporting than in English, particularly in outlets such as Anadolu Ajansı and Yeni Akit, where numerical detail reinforces factual gravity and institutional visibility. Third, the presence of both sharpening and softening, though unevenly distributed, indicates a somewhat broader stylistic repertoire in Turkish news discourse. Sharpening reinforces moral and categorical clarity, whereas softening appears selectively in a single outlet as a form of mitigated evaluation.

From a cross-linguistic perspective, these tendencies align with broader research showing that Turkish media often combine emotionally heightened reporting with strategically deployed evaluative ambiguity depending on ideological orientation (Ercan & Dizdarci, 2016; Özmen, 2019). When compared with English outlets, which rely heavily on intensification and sharpening but avoid softening entirely, Turkish outlets exhibit a more varied set of gradational choices. This variation points to contrasting journalistic cultures: English outlets favour categorical clarity and assertive stance-taking, whereas Turkish outlets balance dramatic emotional engagement with moments of numerical precision and occasional epistemic caution.

Overall, the outlet-level distribution demonstrates that Graduation, particularly Intensification and Quantification, functions as a central organizing resource in Turkish disaster reporting, shaping not only the emotional tone of coverage but also the narrative framing of responsibility, institutional action and

the magnitude of collective loss. Pantti et al. (2012) argue that disaster news is shaped not only by journalistic routines but also by the geopolitics of representation, where national frames, cultural proximity and global hierarchies structure whose suffering becomes visible and how responsibility is assigned. Their discussion of domestication is particularly relevant: news organizations render global or national emergencies meaningful by anchoring them within national identity, political stakes and culturally resonant narratives. This helps explain why Turkish outlets, especially Anadolu Ajansı and Hürriyet, narrate the Kartalkaya fire through heightened emotional proximity, numerical precision and explicit attribution of institutional accountability, whereas English outlets foreground analytical evaluation and institutional scrutiny rather than personalised depictions of victimhood. A number of previous studies have examined Graduation in political, cultural and crime-related contexts (Arunsirot, 2012; Wan, 2024; Fan, 2020; Xia, 2021; Darmawan et al., 2022), often showing that intensification and quantification dominate and that Focus is used to tune certainty, typicality and alignment. The Kartalkaya corpus extends this literature. English and Turkish journalists, like their counterparts in Thai and Indonesian contexts, rely on intensified and quantified language to construct events as urgent, serious and consequential. The patterns observed here are consistent with, but not identical to, those identified in political, cultural and crime reporting across other languages and regions. By situating the Kartalkaya fire within this broader body of research, the study demonstrates that Graduation is a robust analytical lens for understanding how news media calibrate evaluative force across different genres, cultures and institutional settings.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined how English and Turkish news outlets employed Graduation resources in reporting the 2025 Kartalkaya hotel fire, using Appraisal Theory as the analytical framework. By examining Force and Focus across a balanced corpus of thirty articles and conducting outlet-specific comparisons, the analysis showed that both media systems rely extensively on intensification and quantification to construct the severity, urgency and scale of the disaster. At the same time, the findings revealed clear cross-linguistic differences in how categorical precision and epistemic stance are managed through sharpening and softening.

The results demonstrate that Graduation is not a peripheral feature but a core mechanism through which crisis reporting builds evaluative stance. The dominance of Force, particularly intensification, across both corpora corroborates prior research showing that disaster news heightens emotional and moral stakes to mobilize public attention and legitimize institutional action. Beyond confirming these tendencies, the study enriches cross-linguistic Appraisal research by identifying systematic differences in how English and Turkish journalism scale evaluative meanings. Turkish outlets make broader use of numerical scaling and occasionally employ softening to introduce caution or uncertainty, whereas English outlets exclusively adopt up-scaling strategies, combining intensified portrayals with categorical sharpening. These contrasts point to differing journalistic traditions: Turkish reporting tends to foreground emotional involvement and collective grief, while English reporting balances expressive intensity with precise factual calibration and clearer attribution of institutional responsibility. Outlet-level variation further reveals how editorial norms, institutional identity and ideological positioning shape the distribution of Graduation resources within each national media landscape.

Although the study contributes important insights, several limitations should be acknowledged. The corpus is relatively small and restricted to a single disaster event, which limits generalizability across different crisis types or longer reporting cycles. Moreover, the analysis focuses solely on textual patterns and does not account for multimodal features such as images, captions or headline structure, all of which may strongly influence evaluative scaling in disaster coverage. These constraints should be considered when interpreting the findings and when situating them within broader cross-linguistic media analysis.

Future research can extend this work in several ways. Expanding the dataset to include multiple disaster types, additional media systems or longitudinal reporting would allow for more robust generalizations about evaluative scaling in crisis communication. Cross-linguistic comparisons incorporating further languages could illuminate cultural differences in modulating intensity, accountability and emotional proximity. Integrating the Attitude and Engagement systems of Appraisal Theory would offer a more comprehensive view of evaluative stance beyond scaling alone. Multimodal appraisal analysis, in particular, could reveal how visual elements, such as images of destruction, rescue operations or institutional actors, interact with linguistic resources to intensify or mitigate meaning. Finally, given the outlet-level patterns identified in this study, future work might examine how media ownership, ideological alignment and audience expectations influence the strategic use of Graduation in shaping public perception during crises.

By highlighting how journalists linguistically calibrate intensity and precision in disaster reporting, this study underscores the central role of Graduation in shaping how societies interpret catastrophic events. The findings offer a foundation for further inquiry into the evaluative mechanisms through which news discourse constructs urgency, accountability and emotional resonance across cultural and linguistic contexts.

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يمثل هذا الكتاب الإصدار العلمي الرسمي للمؤتمر الدولي التاسع عشر لبحوث اللغة والأدب والثقافة، الذي عُقد في أطلاليا - تركيا خلال الفترة من 4 إلى 8 نوفمبر 2025، بتنظيم من جمعية سايبيلدر وبالشراكة مع عدد من الجامعات والمؤسسات الأكاديمية في تركيا وتونس ودول أخرى. ويضم هذا العمل مجموعة منتقاة من الأبحاث المحكمة التي اجتازت مراحل المراجعة العلمية وفق معايير الجودة والأمانة الأكاديمية.

تعكس الدراسات الواردة في هذا المجلد التنوع المعرفي والغنى المنهجي في مجالات اللغة والأدب والثقافة، كما تبرز قيمة التعاون العلمي الدولي من خلال مشاركة باحثين من ثلاث عشرة دولة. ويؤكد هذا الإصدار أهمية دعم الحراك البحثي متعدد التخصصات وتشجيع الإنتاج العلمي بلغات مختلفة بما يعزز حضور المعرفة في فضاء البحث العالمي.

وإذ نقدّم هذا الكتاب إلى المجتمع الأكاديمي، نعبّر عن تقديرنا للجهات الداعمة والهيئات العلمية والمحكمين والباحثين المشاركين، آمليّن أن يسهم هذا العمل في تعزيز الدراسات ذات الصلة وفتح آفاق جديدة للتعاون الأكاديمي المستدام.

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